

The Impact of Rehabilitation Services on Behaviour Modification of Discharged Inmates:

Lesson from Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano, Kano State.

By

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Abstract

This study determined the rehabilitation services offered to inmates and determined the impact of the services on behavior modification of discharged inmates of Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano State. The study used a correlational survey design in which a population of two thousand three hundred and thirty three (2,333) staff and discharged inmates of the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano were used. Sample for the study was three hundred and six (306) subjects using the table for selecting sample size by the Research Advisers (2006) as a guide. The researcher selected one hundred and two (102) staff and two hundred and four (204) discharged inmates of the Centre using proportionate cluster random sampling and snowballing sampling technique, respectively. Two sets of self-developed multiple-choice questionnaires were designed by the researcher and used for the study. While the questionnaire for the staff of the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano (QSDRC) answered the first research question, the other questionnaire for the discharged inmates from the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano (QDIDRC) has answered the second research question. Both instruments for this study were found valid and reliable at 0.64 and 0.62 levels of coefficient. Data-collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics namely frequency counts and percentages. Findings of the study revealed that the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Centre included Vocational and Psychiatric Rehabilitation, Counseling, and Literacy Education; and the impact of rehabilitation services on behaviour modification of discharged inmates was evidence by re-integration into the family, community, and society; the ability to establish own business and engaged in occupations; and being able to establish and manage own family. The study recommended that Kano State Emergency Relief and Rehabilitation Agency (KSERERA) should introduce a community-based rehabilitation programme (CBRP) which will involve a joint rehabilitation service provision between government and interested voluntary agencies. Also the agency should ensure a well-organized follow-up mechanism so as to discover if there is any constraints that may further need the attention of the Centre so as to intervene in providing solutions to emergent problems regarding adjustment which are common among the discharged inmates in the State.

Introduction

Rehabilitation has been considered a global phenomenon by many societies. In Europe, America and some parts of Asia, many rehabilitation centers have been established to provide services for the control of destitution as a necessity. According to Waddell and Burton (2004), “there has been broad agreement on the importance of rehabilitation, and the need for better occupational health and vocational rehabilitation services in the United Kingdom”, the key features of early intervention include easier access to more skilled labour, support to seek and move into work, the development of new work-focused rehabilitation programmes, and engagement of key stakeholders, and, particularly, employers and family doctors were welcomed by a wide range of organizations. However, there is considerable uncertainty about what ‘rehabilitation’ is, and about its (cost)-effectiveness, particularly for the common health problems that cause the most sickness, absence and long-term incapacity. In the United States cities for instance, the victims of destitution who are the beneficiaries of rehabilitation services include people who engaged in begging. However, in Asia, Chinese cities are among the worst beggar-devastated communities in the world (Hanchu Lu, 1999). The problem which was attributed to urban poverty and uncontrolled rural-urban migration subsided at a time for about three decades when the Communist Government control of the rural urban drift was strict.

Contemporarily, the behaviour of these disturbing populace in the developed and developing societies include begging, squalor, squatting, and destitution across major town and cities, Nigeria is however not an exception on these trend. Sound populations of people in Kano State have for long been suffering with pervasive poverty, particularly in the rural areas of the State, characterized by low income, low agricultural productivity, and food security as well as inadequate health care, housing, education, and nutrition. This trend has led to the tendency for

the rural poor to migrate to the urban centres of Kano State in the hope of securing gainful employment. The consequence is that now there is a much more serious phenomenon of poverty in both the rural and urban sectors in the State. However, the implications of this trend to this study include increase in the level of destitution among various people in the State. This has consequently necessitated the government designing programmes in the rehabilitation institutions for the purpose of providing services that would be targeted on the behaviour modification of these citizens who found wondering on the streets of Kano metropolis.

The Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre was established in 1953, under the then Native Authority, during the reign of the Emir of Kano Alhaji Abdullahi Bayero. The Centre was first situated within the premises of Abdullahi Bayero College, Kano, which is today known as Bayero University Kano. Later the Centre was moved to Dorayi and taken over by the Kano State Government under the auspices of the Ministry of Social Welfare, Youth and Sports. The objectives of the Centre then were to provide accommodation and rehabilitation services to various categories of destitutes; provide counseling services and Psychotherapy; provide medication to inmates who need medical assistance; provide and undertake repatriation of non-indigenes to their various places of origin; provide Vocational Training, and Basic Literacy Education, and provide Personal and Environmental Hygiene to inmates. The goal for rehabilitation services provision contemporarily has been behaviour modification of the inmates who are forced or voluntarily participated in the rehabilitation process. Hence, rehabilitation services provision were regarded as the alternative for the control of street-begging, and destitution which is facilitated by squatting and squalor in the State. The Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, therefore, is among the special institutions that provide active social work practice for resolving behavioural problems in Kano State.

Theoretical framework

The study is based on the I-N-C-O-M-E Theory of Rehabilitation developed by Beveridge, Craddock, Liesener, Stepleton, and Hershenson in 2002. These authors developed a viable alternative theory which guide rehabilitation counseling practice and is considered as a framework that posits that the career development of individuals (including those with disabilities) at any given point in their lives can be classified into one or more statuses, each of which calls for different interventions. These statuses form the acronym INCOME: Imagining, Informing, Choosing, Obtaining, Maintaining, and Exiting.

The implication of this theory to this study is that during the rehabilitation process in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre each of the individual inmates is expected to pass through rigorous stages with an understanding of the procedures similar to those proposed by the I-N-C-O-M-E theory above. For instance, in the ‘Imagining’ procedure individual inmates within the Centre are made to realize there are occupations for them to do: viz. work, jobs, or careers do exist about which they were unaware of or unable to do. At this point an inmate is afforded the training on the basis of which he or she gains experiences and develop the potentialities through rehabilitation services and which improve his or her abilities and capabilities to engage in desired occupations through interaction with the general environment. On the other hand, the ‘Informing’ procedure provides information about him or her, the world of work, existing opportunities, and his or her cultural context to ensure the rehabilitation. The interaction of these factors and the messages obtained from the environment results in the development of career self-efficacy among the inmates in the rehabilitation Centre. The ‘Choosing’ procedure enables the individual inmates integrate the information from the previous statuses and select from among the available occupations. The ability of the individual to choose a career that matches his

or her personality, needs, and abilities is dependent on this information. The role of the counselor of inmates during the choosing procedure is to facilitate the inmate's decision-making process and reconcile the person's disability to this process. In addition, it is common during the 'Obtaining' procedure for the inmate to implement his or her career decision and attain a job which is recognized as a critical outcome of the vocational rehabilitation process in the rehabilitation Centre. The 'Maintaining' procedure involves the process of adapting to, performing, and sustaining a career. 'Maintaining' a career includes components of the person-environment interaction theories which stress that "the process of the person-environment interaction fit is reciprocal, involving the individual shaping the environmental context and the environment influencing the individual" (Rounds and Tracey, 1990). According to Kroll, Dinklage, Lee, Morley, and Wilson (1970) the 'maintaining' is a continual process of working out a synthesis or compromise between the self and reality, opportunities, and limitations of the world. This means that for the inmates, adjustment involves work competences, which consist of work habits, physical and mental skills applicable in work and interpersonal skills applicable in the work setting.

The final procedure in the I-N-C-O-M-E theory is 'Exiting' and which concerns not only getting fired or retiring but also being promoted or departing voluntarily from one's present problem situation to enter a new work setting. In the light of the rehabilitation process in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, therefore, 'Exiting' refers to discharge of the individual inmates after being equipped with knowledge, skills, abilities, and capabilities on the basis of their needs. Whenever the decision to 'exit' is made the role of the rehabilitation professional could involve helping the individual inmates to secure jobs or desired occupations that will ensure the betterments of the discharged inmates.

Conceptual Framework

The Concept of Rehabilitation

Rehabilitation, technically, is a creative procedure which includes the cooperative intervention by various social work specialists and associates in health, technical, environmental, and other fields, to improve the physical, mental, social and vocational status of the disabled, with the objectives of preserving and improving their capacities to live happily and productively at an optimum level, and being offered similar opportunities as their neighbours (Krusen, Kottke, and Elwood 1971; Olaogun, 2007). In other words, it is a process of decreasing the dependence of the disabled person by developing, to the greatest extent possible, the abilities needed for adequate functioning in his individual situations in the local community (Helinder, 1984).

According to Sink (1979) rehabilitation is the process by which medical, psychological, social, vocational and educational services are utilized by persons with physical and or mental disabilities for the purpose of attaining maximum independence. Rehabilitation could also be said to be a generic field of practice designed to assist people with disabilities in their restoration to the fullest, physical, mental, social, vocational and economic functioning, that they are capable of attaining (Hamilton, 1950). Socially, in countries like Nigeria, rehabilitation addresses the problem of one form of disability or the other through preventing or stopping the subject from becoming or remaining as beggars.

The Concept of Behaviour Modification

Since modification refers to reform, change, or altering a phenomena; behaviour modification is empirically referring to demonstrate behaviour change techniques to increase or decrease the frequency of behaviours. According to Akinade (2012) include “altering an

individual's behaviours and reactions to stimuli through positive and negative reinforcement of adaptive behaviour through its extinction, punishment and/or satiation". Psychologists have many interpretations on the concept of behaviour modification in various studies. While Skinner (1953) sees behaviour modification as the application of operant conditioning techniques to modify human behaviour, recent scholar Anastesi (1982, cited in Akinade, 2012) sees it as a direct use of major learning principles in a management of a behavioural change. In addition to this, behaviour modification is regarded as "effort to change human behaviour and emotion in a beneficial way according to the principles of learning" (Yalom, 1970, cited in Akinade, 2012).

However, the role of rehabilitation counselors and psychotherapists in rehabilitation Centres were to make effective utilization of their skills towards providing behaviour modification treatment in the rehabilitation process. This would assure behavioural changes and adjustment of the discharged inmates from the rehabilitation Centres.

Statement of the Problem

Rehabilitation is not only concerned with physical or functional restoration or compensation of individuals disabled by injury or disease. According to Olaogun, Nyante, and Ajediran, (2009) attention is also given to the total quality of life in terms of wellness, happiness and satisfaction in fulfilling the demands and needs of and capabilities towards human development in terms of orientation; freedom of movement; independence; expression of self (with respect to age, sex and culture), relationship and ability to ensure independent economic existence. In other words, even after a serious injury, illness or surgery, one need to recover completely. This means that, there is the need to regain strength, to relearn skills or find new ways of doing things one did before.

Government of Nigeria at various levels has made several attempts to control destitution in towns, cities, and rural communities through the establishment of rehabilitation centers which are targeted for many clients. Contemporarily, adequate resources have been effectively utilized in the provision of modern rehabilitation services aimed at restoring people's capacities to function more effectively within their living environment. Such rehabilitation services include vocational skills acquisition programmes designed for the disabled persons and catering services for women who have been abandoned caring for children.

The Dorayi rehabilitation centre, Kano, was established before the independence of Nigeria. Apart from other rehabilitation programmes taking place in psychiatric rehabilitation centres, blind centres among others, today the Dorayi rehabilitation centre is an institution which is fully engaged in the effective delivery of various services for those men and women who are found wandering in the metropolis. The aim of these services delivery is to equip individuals with appropriate skills and knowledge to fully engage in the socio-economic development of the State. In every individual, no matter the deficiency there is potentiality for some socio-economic activity. It was on this basis that, the researcher conducted a study to examine the impact of rehabilitation services on behaviour modification of discharged inmates of Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano, Kano State that are found roaming the streets in towns and cities or brought by relatives and authorities from different parts of Kano State.

The objectives of this study are:

- i) To determine the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano.

- ii) To determine the impact of rehabilitation services on behaviour modification of discharged inmates of Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano.

The following research questions are answered in this study:

- i) What are the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano?
- ii) What is the impact of rehabilitation services on behaviour modification of discharged inmates of Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano?

Methodology

This study employed a correlational survey study in which a population of two thousand three hundred and thirty three (2333) staff and discharged inmates of the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre subjects were used. Three hundred and six (306) subjects were derived as sample as guided by the table for selecting sample size by the Research Advisers (2006). The subjects were captured using proportionate cluster sampling technique where the staff and discharged inmates of the Centre were allocated one hundred and two (102), and two hundred and four (204) subjects, respectively. However, the procedure adopted in selecting sample from the one hundred and two (102) subjects was through the simple random technique. While the two hundred and four (204) discharged inmates of the Centre were selected from using a snowballing technique. Two sets of self-developed multiple-choice questionnaires were used for the study, viz. questionnaires for the staff of the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre (QSDRC) and questionnaire for the Discharged Inmates of Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre (QDIDRC). These instruments were validated by the professionals in measurement and evaluations, the reliability of the questionnaires was obtained using PPMC and the coefficients were at 0.64 and 0.62 levels.

Data-collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics in simple frequency counts and percentages.

Results Presentation and Data Analysis

Research Question 1: What are the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano?

This research question was answered by the staff. Frequencies and percentages used in the analysis and the data is presented in Table 1 where n=102.

Table 1. The rehabilitation services offered to inmates in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano

The rehabilitation services offered to inmates	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1. Availability of Rehabilitation Services in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre	Available	102	100
2. Rehabilitation Services offered to Inmates in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre	a) Vocational Rehabilitation	32	31.4
	b) Psychiatric Rehabilitation	26	25.5
	c) Counseling	27	26.5
	d) Literacy Education	15	14.7
	e) Others: (Psychotherapy)	2	2.0
3. Delivery techniques	a) Classroom Instruction	14	13.7
	b) Clinical Nursing	15	14.7
	c) Tutelage	35	34.3
	d) Workshop Practice	34	33.3
	e) Others: (Drama and Role-playing)	4	3.9
4. Other Services Recommended for the Centre	a) Follow-up Services	45	44.1
	b) Community Based Rehabilitation Services	36	35.3
	c) A Joint Rehabilitation Service between the Centre and the community	21	20.6

Interpretation:

The table 1 presents data on rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre. The table shows that all the one hundred and two (102) staff respondents participated in the provision of Rehabilitation Services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano.

In addition to this, the table shows that the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi rehabilitation Centre Kano were vocational rehabilitation (31.4%); psychiatric rehabilitation (25.5%); counseling services (26.5%); literacy education (14.7%), and psychotherapy (2%). Moreover, the table indicates that the services were provided to inmates through different methodologies, e.g. Classroom Instructions (13.7%), Clinical Nursing (14.7%), Tutelage (34.3%), Workshop Practice (33.3%), and Drama and Role-playing (3.9%).

Finally, the table above shows that all the one hundred and two (102) respondents recommended more services for the Centre; 45 (44.1%) recommended for Follow-up services; 36 (35.3%) recommended Community-Based Rehabilitation services, and (20.6%) recommended for a Joint Rehabilitation Service between the Centre and the Community.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of rehabilitation services on behaviour modification of discharged inmates of Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano?

This research question was however, answered by the discharged inmates and analyzed using frequencies and simple percentages as shown in the Table 2 where n=204.

Table 2. The impact of rehabilitation services on behaviour modification of discharged inmates of Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano

The behaviour modification of discharged inmates	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1. Present state of mental health	a) Adjusted	133	65.2
	b) Fairly adjusted	57	27.9
	c) Not yet adjusted	14	6.9
2. Moral values acquired from the Centre	a) Performing the daily prayers and listening of religious preaching	93	45.6
	b) Respecting Elders	63	30.9
	c) Avoiding bad company	45	22.1
	d) Others: (usefully living with parents)	03	1.5
3. Attitudinal change experienced	a) Re-integration in to the family, community, and society	91	44.6
	b) The ability to established own business and engaged in occupations	67	32.9
	c) Being able to establish and manage own family	46	22.5

Interpretation:

According to table 2 most of the respondents (65.2%) believed that they were better adjusted; (27.9%) of the respondents were fairly adjusted, and only fourteen (6.9%) said they were yet to be adjusted. It is note-worthy that most inmates (98%) experience behaviour change. Moreover, the distribution as regards the moral values acquired by the respondents from the Centre, according to the table, shows performing the daily prayers and listening to religious preaching (45.6%); respecting elders (30.9%); avoiding bad company (22.1%), and usefully living with parents (1.5%), in the other category. It is important to note too that, the type of skills

acquired by the respondents from the Centre, according to the table, were reading and writing (16.2%); and vocational occupations, and the better of which were the highest number (58.3%). Moreover, the respondents who learned skills in Knowledge in Social Interaction from among the discharged respondents were 15.7%, while the remaining 9.8% belong to those, in the other category, who had engaged in occupations. Furthermore, the table indicated that, relative to the attitudinal change experienced by the respondents from the Centre from counseling services include re-integration into their family, community, and society (44.6%), while the respondents who experienced the ability to establish own businesses and engaged in occupations were 32.9% and those respondents who were able to establish and manage own family were 22.5%. From this therefore, it has been deduced that behaviour modification was evident.

Summary of findings

From the preceding data analysis, the following is the summary of findings:

- i) The rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano were Vocational Rehabilitation, Psychiatric Rehabilitation, Counseling, and Literacy Education; as a result of moral values acquired in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre.
- ii) The impact of rehabilitation services on behaviour modification of discharged inmates of Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano was evidence by re-integration into the family, community, and society; the ability to establish own business and engaged in occupations; and being able to establish and manage own family.

Discussion of Results

The first finding of the study is that the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano were Vocational Rehabilitation, Psychiatric Rehabilitation,

Counseling, and Literacy Education. This was however, in contrast with the rehabilitation services before independence. According to historical sources in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, when it was established in 1953, under the then Native Authority during the reign of the Emir of Kano Alhaji Abdullahi Bayero, services offered to inmates included provision of Counseling and Psychotherapy, Medication, Repatriation, Vocational Training, Basic Literacy Education, and Sanitation and Health Education. During this period, there was an insufficiency of professional workers in the Centre. Moreover, there were other rehabilitation centres in Nigeria where services were offered to inmates which differed significantly from those offered now in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano. Some of the Centres in the South then had been engaged in the provision of sufficient nutrition, health, vocational skills acquisition training, and counseling, among others, to inmates, for instance, the Atanda Olu School Surulere, Lagos; the Cheshire Home Oluyole, Ibadan; and the Rehabilitation Centre Moniya Ibadan, to mention a few. In addition to this, under the current welfare situation, the rise in the level of personnel in Social work practice and social welfare education as well as government involvement in the establishment of rehabilitation Centres across the States of the Federation, makes Kano State not an exception in the rehabilitation services provision. However, the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano according to the findings of this research, is committed to offering rehabilitation services to inmates in a more comprehensive manner, through the efforts of various professionals and specialist in different fields. Relative to the Vocational Rehabilitation, Psychiatric Rehabilitation, Counseling, and Literacy Education services offered in the Dorayi rehabilitation Centre, Kano. Sabo Indabawa (2000) opined that, for the destitutes, a major recommendation was for there to be greater opportunities for basic education, with an emphasis on vocational competence. Disabled people have the same right to basic education which connotes fundamentals and reflect

those aspects of behaviour modification required by the individual, without which he/she would be so handicapped that he/she would be living at the periphery of the society, neither benefiting from it nor contributing to its welfare and improvement (Fafunwa, 1990).

Regarding the impact of rehabilitation services on behaviour modification of discharged inmates of Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, re-integration into the family, community, and society, the ability to establish own business and engaged in occupations, as well as being able to establish and manage own family were some of the changes found. This relates with the fact that most of these inmates who received the rehabilitation services from the Centre required effective counseling services which leads to modifying their behaviour in each of the services offered to them. Therefore the effectiveness of modification of the behaviour of inmates from the rehabilitation Centre determines their quality of performance in family, community and societal developmental activities. According to the findings, most discharged inmates from the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, have become more knowledgeable in social and economic activities which had been targeted in the promotion of their lives. The findings of this research also proved that many of the discharged inmates had successfully re-integrated into the society and their families, with higher hopes in their minds, hence they were prepared to utilize the knowledge and skills learned to increase income and play key roles in their families and communities. Although, initially, they have had bad associates, as well as been roaming in the streets of urban areas engaged in begging and other social vices, after being discharged from the Centre they had begun relating to good friends, more regularly performing prayers, as well as better appreciating other members of the community. In the light of these, therefore, it is important to note that discharged inmates behaviour has been modified. And they had begun to be part of the entire

community through their effort of willingness to participate in the social, political and economic activities of the society.

Conclusion and Recommendation:

There is no doubt that for decades rehabilitation has been an effective way for ensuring social resources development for inmates in the so-called developed and developing countries. Development scholars are optimistic that every individual, no matter his or her deficiencies, there is a potentiality for development. It is, however, necessary also for rehabilitation services to bring out something or encourage newer potentialities in the individuals to achieve maximum desired behaviour modification and actions that could promote the wellbeing of such individuals within the context of their societies.

This study recommended that the Kano State Emergency Relief and Rehabilitation Agency (KSERERA) should introduce a community-based rehabilitation programme (CBRP) which will involve a joint rehabilitation service provision between government and interested voluntary agencies, including philanthropists and other members of the community. The aim here is to utilize both economic and social resources of the community in effectively solving the problems of discharged inmates, so that they can resettle, and by extension the entire community. And the agency should ensure a well-organized follow-up mechanism so as to discover if there is any constraints that may further need the attention of the Centre so as to intervene in providing solutions to emergent problems which are common among the discharged inmates in State.

References

- Akinade, E. A. (2012) *Modern Behaviour Modification*. Principles and Practices. Ibadan Nigeria. Brightways Publishers
- Beveridge, S., Craddock, S. H., Liesener J., Stepleton, M. & Hershenson, D. (2002) Income: A framework for Conceptualizing the Career Development of Persons with Disabilities. *Rehabilitation Counselling Bulletin*, Volume 45, Number 4, p. 1-21
- Fafunwa, A. B. (1990) Opening Address Delivered at the National Conference on Education For All, organised by *NERDC*, Abeokuta, Nigeria.
- Hamilton, K. W. (1950). *Counseling the Handicapped in the Rehabilitation Process*. NewYork. USA. Ronald Press.
- Helinder, E. (1984). The principles of community-based rehabilitation. *Quaderni di cooperazione sanitaria* – Health Cooperation 11, pp.35-41.
- Hanchao L. (1999). Becoming Urban: Mendicancy and Vagrants in Modern Shanghai. *Journal of Social History*. [http// www.shanghaiCentre.com](http://www.shanghaiCentre.com).
- Indabawa, S. (2000). Overcoming Destitution through Literacy. A Case of the Disabled Persons Literacy Programme in Kano State, Nigeria. *Journal of Social Development in Africa*. 15, I, pp. 15-
- Kroll, A. M., Dinklade, L. B., Lee, J., Morley, E. D. & Wilson, E.H. (1970) *Career Development: Growth and Crisis*. New York: Wiley
- Krusen, F. H., Kottke, F. J. & Elwood, P. M. (1971). Handbook of Physical Medicine And Rehabilitation. *The American Rehabilitation Foundation*. Toronto, USA.WB Saunders, pp. 1-10.
- Olaogun, M. O. B., Nyante, G. G. G., Ajediran, A. I. (2009). Overcoming the Barriers for Participation by the Disabled. An appraisal and global view of communitybased rehabilitation in community development. *AJPARS*. 1, No. 1 pp. 24-29.
- Research Advisers (2006) Table for Determining Sample from a given Population, USA Research Advisers,
- Rounds, J.B. & Tracey, T. j. (1990) *From trait-and-factor to person-environment fit Counselling: Theory and Process*. In W.B. Walsh & S.H. Osipow (Eds), *Career Counselling: Contemporary Topics in Vocational Psychology* (pp.1-44)
- Sink, I. (1977). Trends in Rehabilitation. *Journal of Rehabilitation*. 1, No. 43 pp. 36-40
- Skinner, B.F. (1953) *Science and Human, Behaviour*. New York. MacMillan
- Waddell, G. & Burton, A. K. (2004). *Concepts of Rehabilitation for the Management of Common Health Problems*. London, TSO.